

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for CDK5 (Q00535) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

Cyclin-dependent kinase 5 (CDK5) is a proline-directed serine/threonine kinase that plays a critical role in the development and function of the central nervous system. Here we have characterized thirteen CDK5 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q00535, *CDK5*, CDK5, CDKN5, Cyclin-dependent kinase 5, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

CDK5 is a neuron-specific serine/threonine kinase that plays a pivotal role in maintaining neuronal structure and synaptic function [1]. Its activity is tightly regulated by association with activator proteins such as p35 [2]. In the context of Parkinson's disease (PD), pathological stressors including oxidative damage and mitochondrial dysfunction promote the cleavage of p35 into p25, leading to prolonged and aberrant activation of CDK5 [3].

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data [4]. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein [4]. Here we characterized thirteen commercial CDK5 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence (also referred to as immunocytochemistry), enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of CDK5 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway [5] and in Table 4 of this data note [4].

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells [6, 7]. The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off [8]. The HAP1 cell line expresses the *CDK5* transcript at $4.9 \log_2$ TPM+1. A HAP1 *CDK5* KO cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1). A HEK293T *CDK5* KO line is also available at Abcam (Table 1). The HAP1 line was used for the complete antibody screening, and as seen on DepMap, the HAP1 does not carry mutations in the *CDK5* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

Two recombinant antibodies were first tested to compare the levels of CDK5 expression in HAP1 and HEK293T (Figure 1A). To screen all thirteen by western blot, HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the thirteen CDK5 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1B).

We then assessed the capability of all thirteen antibodies to capture CDK5 from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific CDK5 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, thirteen antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the CDK5 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis [4].

In conclusion, we have screened thirteen CDK5 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications [8]. High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect CDK5 were identified in western blot and immunofluorescence. Researchers who wish to study CDK5 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available CDK5 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in CDK5, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. CDK5 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io (protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization) [4]. Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) [9, 10]. All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated with the membrane in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Culture medium was removed, and cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL) at room temperature for 15 min. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked in PBS1x with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS1x, 5% BSA, 0.01% Triton X-100) containing the primary CDK5 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with the corresponding Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibody in IF buffer for 1 hr at room temperature. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with PBS1x then incubated with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) and washed once with PBS1x.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.94 air objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification [11]. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability*Underlying data*

Zenodo: Dataset for the CDK5 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC005189c010	CVCL_SI38	HAP1	<i>CDK5</i> KO
Abcam	ab255449	CVCL_0063	HEK293T	WT
Abcam	ab266089	CVCL_B2U1	HEK293T	<i>CDK5</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the CDK5 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abbexa	abx422613*	A2511457	AB_3736737	monoclonal	M196	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF, other
Abcam	ab40773**	1091056-20	AB_726779	recombinant mono	EP715Y	rabbit	0.24	Wb, IP, IF, other
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38525_T100	QC8200-42482	AB_842039	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP38526_T100	QC8201-40668	AB_842040	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, other
Aviva Systems Biology	AVARP03025_P050	QC0107-90401	AB_2045352	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb, other
Cell Signaling Technology	14145**	4	AB_2773717	recombinant mono	D1F7M	rabbit	0.27	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX108328	39750	AB_2036536	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF, other
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1980**	Q4039305	AB_3741464	recombinant mono	1H13	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF
Proteintech	10430-1-AP	00072655	AB_2078859	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.80	Wb, IP, IF, other
Proteintech	68514-1-Ig*	10040385	AB_3085223	monoclonal	1B9E1	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF, other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-31987**	79532263	AB_2809281	recombinant mono	SR39-01	rabbit	1.00	Wb, other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35214**	79531622	AB_2849118	recombinant mono	7C8T10	rabbit	0.64	Wb, other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-53156**	79532368	AB_3247629	recombinant mono	23GB1425	rabbit	1.60	Wb, IF, other

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead)</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not captured in the IP</p>	<p>WT/KO cell mosaic</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>Target protein detected (white staining)</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., *Elife*, 2023 [8]

A. HAP1 and HEK293T

B. screening in HAP1

GTX108328 ZRB1980** 10430-1-AP 68514-1-Ig* MA5-31987** MA5-35214** MA5-53156**

Figure 1: CDK5 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: CDK5 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: CDK5 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: CDK5 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HAP1 and HEK293T (WT and *CDK5* KO) were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated CDK5 antibodies. ab40773** was used at 1/2000, and 14145** at 1/1000.

B) Lysates of HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO were processed for western blot with the indicated CDK5 antibodies. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: abx422613* at 1/1000, ab40773** at 1/2000, ARP38525_T100 at 1/1000, ARP38526_T100 at 1/1000, AVARP03025_P050 at 1/500, 14145** at 1/1000, GTX108328 at 1/1000, ZRB1980** at 1/1000, 10430-1-AP at 1/1000, 68514-1-Ig* at 1/5000, MA5-31987** at 1/1000, MA5-35214** at 1/500, MA5-53156** at 1/2000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Predicted band size: 33.3 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: CDK5 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated CDK5 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the CDK5 antibody ab40773** used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 3: CDK5 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *CDK5* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Culture medium was removed, and cell were fixed with 4% PFA for 15 min. Cells were permeabilized with 0.1% Triton-X100 for 10 min, and stained with the indicated CDK5 antibodies and with the corresponding Fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody then with DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution and at 1 or 2 µg/ml. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: abx422613* at 1/1000, ab40773** at 1/250, ARP38525_T100 at 1/1000, ARP38526_T100 at 1/1000, AVARP03025_P050 at 1/500, 14145** at 1/250, GTX108328 at 1/200, ZRB1980** at 1/100, 10430-1-AP at 1/1500, 68514-1-Ig* at 1/1000, MA5-31987** at 1/1000, MA5-35214** at 1/650, MA5-53156** at 1/1500. Bars = 10 µm. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.